

Isocoumarins : Part—IX*. 3-Phenylisocoumarins and synthesis of 3-phenyl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarins, 3-phenylisochromenes and 3-phenylisochromans

Sneha Gulgule and R. N. Usgaonkar

3-Phenylisocoumarins have been used to synthesise 3-phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins, 3-phenylisochromenes and 3-phenylisochromans. Reduction with sodium borohydride of 2-carboxybenzyl phenyl ketones obtained from 3-phenylisocoumarins, gave the dihydroisocoumarins. Grignard reaction on 3-phenylisocoumarins gave the isochromenes and catalytic reduction of isochromenes provided the isochromans.

3-Phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin derivatives are known to occur in nature e.g., Phylodulcinol and Hydrangenol¹, which are isolated from the plant *Hydrangea macrophylla* whereas 3-phenylisochromenes and isochromans are the oxygen heterocycles on which practically little information is available in the literature^{2,3,4,5}. 3-Phenylisocoumarins which can now be obtained in good yields⁶ have been used as intermediates in the synthesis devised for these interesting oxygen heterocycles.

7-Methoxy-3-phenylisocoumarins (I) on treating with aq. NaOH provide corresponding 2-carboxybenzyl phenyl ketones⁶ (II) reduction of these ketones with NaBH₄ in methanolic solution followed by acidification gave 7-methoxy 3-phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (III) directly in excellent yield by lactonisation of the resulting carbinol. Various 7-methoxy-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins, very much similar to the naturally occurring ones, differing only in the position of substituents have thus been synthesised in excellent yield.

In case of the 3-phenylisocoumarin derivatives (I) with free -OH on the phenyl nucleus, a large excess of NaBH₄ was found necessary for effecting the reduction.

Investigations of the action of CH₃MgI on various 7-methoxy-3-phenylisocoumarins (I) showed that the corresponding 1,1-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylisochromenes (II) are formed in good yield when more than 2 moles of CH₃MgI per mole of the isocoumarin is used in the reaction. The reactions were carried out using benzene admixed with dry ether as

* Part VIII, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **47**, 192.

1. Y. Asahina and J. Asano, *Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 171; 1930, **63**, 429; 1931, **64**, 1252.
2. J. N. Chatterjee, *Ber.*, 1958, **91**, 2636; J. N. Chatterjee, B. K. Banerjee and N. C. Jha, *Ber.*, 1965, **98**, 3275.
3. J. N. Chatterjee and H. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 443.
4. C. F. H. Allen and J. W. Gates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1230.
5. R. L. Shriner, H. W. Johnston and C. E. Koslow, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, **19**, 204.
6. S. P. Inamdar and R. N. Usgaonkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 615.

solvent. It was observed, however, that when free -OH group was present on the 3-phenyl-isocoumarin, the reaction did not go smoothly to yield corresponding isochromene even when large excess of CH_3MgI was used to account for its secondary reaction with free -OH group. An intractable tarry material resulted. In case of 7-methoxy-3-(4-hydroxy) phenylisocoumarin (Ie), the action of CH_3MgI could be carried out to give the corresponding isochromene (IVe) by first protecting the free -OH group in the isocoumarin by acetylation and then carrying out the reaction on the acetoxy isocoumarin using CH_3MgI (more than 6 moles) in large excess. The corresponding hydroxy isochromene (IVe) was formed in good yield with cleavage of the acetoxy group in the reaction. This method however was not very successful in other cases. Protection of -OH group in the isocoumarins by benzylation gave good results and the corresponding benzyloxyisochromenes were obtained in good yield. The cleavage of the benzyloxy group to generate hydroxy isochromenes however presented difficulties. Reductive cleavage of the benzyloxy group with $H_2/Raney Ni$ or $H_2/Pd-C$ at atmospheric pressure which were successfully used in our laboratories for cleavage of the benzyloxy chromenes⁷ was not successful and the original isochromenes were recovered unchanged, not only at atmospheric pressure but also when the hydrogenation was carried out at 45 lbs, pressure. The olefinic double bond of these benzyloxy isochromenes also did not get reduced under these conditions.

Shriner *et al.*⁵ and Allen and Gates⁶ reported the formation of isobenzopyrillium salt by interaction of isocoumarin with a Grignard reagent. The latter authors isolated a carbinol derivative with excess of the reagent. Mukherjee *et al.*³ who investigated indenoisocoumarins,

found that with 2 moles of CH_3MgI or PhMgI the corresponding indenoisochromenes are formed but if one mole of the Grignard reagent is used, the corresponding isobenzopyrillium salt can be isolated.

The formation of isochromene from isocoumarin with 2 moles of Grignard reagent may be explained as given below :

In the reactions that have been studied, in the present work, it was found that to get optimum yields, CH_3I and Mg are to be used in excess in the preparation of CH_3MgI due to the volatility of CH_3I . Quantities that were used were nearly what would be required to generate about 4 moles of CH_3MgI

The 7-methoxy-1,1-dimethyl-3-phenylisochromenes (IV) were converted into the corresponding 7-methoxy-1,1-dimethyl-3-phenylisochromans (V) quantitatively by catalytic reduction of the olefinic double bond with hydrogen over Pd/C at 45 lbs. pressure thus providing a good synthesis for these oxygen heterocycles. The reduction was not however successful in case of the benzyloxyisochromenes in which probably the bulky groups present on the molecule sterically hindered the approach of hydrogen to the olefinic double bond.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Methoxy-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (III) (general procedure) : 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl phenyl ketone derivative (II) dissolved in methanol/ethanol was treated with NaBH_4 in small lots with shaking and then left aside at room temperature for 3 hrs. It was then acidified with HCl , diluted with water and the separated solid was washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 , then with water and crystallised from appropriate solvent.

The following 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins are thus synthesised :

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(4-methoxy)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIc) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl 4-methoxyphenyl ketone⁶ (IIc) (0.5 g. in 20 ml. of methanol) and NaBH₄ (0.4 g.). It was crystallized from methanol as needles, m.p. 158–59°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 71.2; H, 5.5; C₁₉H₁₆O₄ requires : C, 71.4; H, 5.6%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(4-ethoxy)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIId) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl 4-ethoxyphenyl ketone⁶ (IIId) (0.5 g. in 20 ml. methanol) and NaBH₄ (0.4 g.). It crystallised from aq. methanol, needles, m.p. 103–04°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 72.5; H, 6.7. C₁₈H₁₈O₄ requires : C, 72.5; H, 6.7%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(4-hydroxy)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIe) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl 4-hydroxyphenyl ketone⁶ (IIe) (0.5 g. and NaBH₄ 0.6 g.). It crystallised from methanol as prisms, yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 71.3; H, 5.3%. C₁₆H₁₄O₄ requires : C, 71.0; H, 5.2%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(3-isopropyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIIf) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl 3-isopropyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylphenyl ketone⁶ (IIIf) (0.5 g.) and NaBH₄ (0.65 g.). It crystallised from methanol, m.p. 183–85°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 74.0; H, 7.0%. C₂₀H₂₂O₄ requires : C, 73.6; H, 6.7%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(4-hydroxy-3-methyl)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIg) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl 4-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl ketone⁶ (IIg) (0.5 g. in 40 ml. ethanol) and NaBH₄ (0.8 g.). It crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 196–97°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 71.4; H, 5.4%. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires : C, 71.8; H, 5.6%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIh) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl-2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl ketone⁶ (IIh) (0.5 g. in 40 ml. ethanol) and NaBH₄ (0.8 g.). It crystallised from aq. methanol (85%), m.p. 180–82°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 71.4; H, 5.4%. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires : C, 71.8; H, 5.6%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-(4-methyl)phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIb) : from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl 4-methylphenyl ketone⁶ (IIb) (0.5 g. in 25 ml. methanol) and NaBH₄ (0.4 g.). It crystallised from aq. methanol, needles, m.p. 118–19°. Yield 0.35 g. (Found : C, 76.6; H, 5.9%. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires : C, 76.1; H, 5.9%).

(±) 7-Methoxy-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (IIIa) ; from 2-carboxy-4-methoxybenzyl phenyl ketone⁶ (IIa) (0.5 g. in 20 ml. methanol) and NaBH₄ (0.4 g.). It crystallised from methanol, m.p. 120–22°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 75.6; H, 5.4%. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ requires : C, 75.5; H, 5.1%).

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylisochromenes (IV) (general procedure). A solution of 7-methoxy-3-phenylisocoumarin (I) in dry benzene was gradually added to the solution of methyl magnesium iodide in dry ether-benzene at room temperature with stirring. After removal of ether by distillation, the mixture was refluxed overnight on water bath; cooled and poured on crushed ice and HCl. The benzene layer and the aq. layer was separated and the aq. layer was repeatedly extracted with benzene and the extract mixed with original

benzene layer was well washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solution was concentrated to a small bulk when crystalline solid separated. It was then recrystallised from appropriate solvent.

The following 3-phenylisochromenes are thus synthesised.

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-methoxy)phenylisochromene (IVc) : from 7-methoxy-3-(4-methoxy)phenylisocoumarin⁶ (Ic) (1 g. in 50 ml. of benzene) and CH_3MgI [Mg(0.5 g.) and CH_3I (2 g.) in ether-benzene (8 ml.+10 ml.)]. It crystallised from ethanol as shining plates, m.p. 109–10°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 76.6; H, 6.8%. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 77.0; H, 6.75%). UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 230 and 330 nm (log ϵ 4.23 and 4.5).

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-ethoxy)phenylisochromene (IV) : from 7-methoxy-3-(4-ethoxy)phenylisocoumarin (Id) (1 g. in 50 ml. of dry benzene) and CH_3MgI [Mg (0.6 g.) and CH_3I (3.5 g.) in ether-benzene (8 ml.+10 ml.)]. It crystallised from methanol as plates, m.p. 93–94°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 77.6; H, 7.5%. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 77.4; H, 7.1%).

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-hydroxy)phenylisochromene (IVe) : from 7-methoxy-3-(4-acetoxy)phenylisocoumarin (1 g. in 35 ml. benzene) and CH_3MgI [Mg (0.85 g.), CH_3I (6 g.) and ether-benzene (10 ml.+10 ml.)]. It crystallised from aq. ethanol (60%), m.p. 82–84°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 74.9; H, 6.6%. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 75.1; H, 6.4%).

7-Methoxy-3-(4-acetoxy)phenylisocoumarin was prepared by refluxing 7-methoxy-3-(4-hydroxy)phenylisocoumarin⁶ (Ie) (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (4 ml.) and a drop of pyridine for about an hour, then poured on crushed ice+HCl and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 218–19°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 67.0; H, 4.8%. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 67.2; H, 4.6%).

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(2-isopropyl-4-benzyloxy-6-methyl)-phenylisochromene (IVf) : from 7-methoxy-3-(3-isopropyl-4-benzyloxy-6-methyl)phenylisocoumarin (If₁) (1 g. in 50 ml. of benzene) and CH_3MgI [Mg (0.45 g.), CH_3I (3.5 g.) and ether-benzene (10 ml.+8 ml.)]. It was distilled under reduced pressure, oily liquid b.p. 74–8°/2–2.5 mm. (Found : C, 80.8; H, 7.9%. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 81.3; H, 7.4%).

The benzyloxy isocoumarin (If₁) was prepared by refluxing 7-methoxy-3-(3-isopropyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl)phenylisocoumarin⁶ (If) (1 g.) in acetone (25 ml.) with benzyl chloride (6 ml.) and anhydrous Na_2CO_3 (1 g.) overnight. After filtering, the solution was concentrated to a small bulk and the separating solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 126–28°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 78.4; H, 6.4%. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 78.2; H, 6.2%).

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-benzyloxy-3-methyl)phenylisochromene (IVg) was prepared from 7-methoxy-3-(4-benzyloxy-3-methyl)phenylisocoumarin (Ig) (1 g. in 30 ml. of benzene) and CH_3MgI [Mg(0.45), CH_3I (3.5 g.) and ether-benzene (10 ml.+8 ml.)]. It crystallised from methanol, m.p. 116–17°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 81.2; H, 6.6%. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 80.8; H, 6.8%).

The benzyloxyisocoumarin (Ig₁) was prepared by refluxing 7-methoxy-3-(4-hydroxy-3-methyl)phenylisocoumarin⁶ (Ig) in dry acetone (30 ml.) with benzyl chloride (5 ml.) and anhydrous Na_2CO_3 (1 g.) overnight, and after filtering the solution was concentrated to

a small bulk and the separating solid crystallised from methanol, m.p. 149–51°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 77.0; H, 5.5%. $C_{24}H_{20}O_4$ requires : C, 77.4; H, 5.3%).

1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-methyl)phenylisochromene (IVb) : from 7-methoxy-3-(4-methyl)phenylisocoumarin⁶ (IIb) (1 g. in 50 ml. of benzene) and CH_3MgI [Mg (0.5 g., CH_3I (3 g.) in ether-benzene (10 ml.+8 ml.)]. It crystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 69–71°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 81.8; H, 7.3%. $C_{19}H_{20}O_2$ requires : C, 81.5; H, 7.1%).

7-Methoxy-3-phenylisochromans (V) : (*general procedure*) : Palladised charcoal (0.01 g., 30%) was added to the ethanolic solution of 1,1-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylisochromenes (IV) (0.2 g. in 50 ml.) and it was hydrogenated by passing H_2 gas under pressure of 45 lbs/sq. inch for 2 hrs. at room temperature with shaking. The mixture was then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to a small bulk and the separating solid was crystallised from appropriate solvent.

The following isochromans are thus prepared from the corresponding isochromenes (IV).

(±) *1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-methoxy)phenylisochroman* (Vc) : It crystallised from aq. ethanol (60%), m.p. 118–20°, yield 0.18 g. (Found : C, 76.4; H, 6.9%. $C_{19}H_{22}O_3$ requires : C, 76.4; H, 7.3%).

(±) *1,1-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-(4-ethoxy)phenylisochroman* (Vc) : crystallised from aq. ethanol (65%), m.p. 98–99°. Yield 0.18 g. (Found : C, 77.0; H, 7.4%. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3$ requires : C, 76.9; H, 7.6%).

The authors offer their thanks to Mrs. J. A. Patankar for microanalyses.

Organic Chemistry,
Research Laboratory,
Institute of Science,
Bombay-32.

Received April 23, 1971